

(Effect of Gender on Academic Achievement in Algebraic Expressions ...Ezekiel, O. O. Et. al. 2025)

Effect of Gender on Academic Achievement in Algebraic Expression Concept among Federal Colleges of Education Students in South-west, Nigeria

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Abstract

Students' achievement in Algebraic expressions over the years have not been encouraging as a concept under Basic General Mathematics II course for students in all Federal Colleges of Education, Nigeria. This may be due to so many factors like large class-size, crowded classrooms, misinterpretation of word problems, gender differences, teaching methodologies employed by the lecturers and other factors. Many scholars had worked on these variables but not many investigated effects of gender on Federal Colleges of Education students' academic achievement in Algebraic expressions in Southwest, Nigeria. Social Learning and Lev Vygotsky's were used for this study. Mixed method which involves quasi-experimental design was used. The population for the study comprised all the 100 level Students in Federal Colleges of Education Southwest, Nigeria. A multi-stage sampling technique was used to select the participants for the study. Two research instruments were used: Basic General Mathematics Students' Academic Achievement Test (BGMSAAT), and a Lesson Plan Format (LPF). One hypothesis was formulated and tested using Analysis of Covariance at a 0.05 level of significance. The result shown that: Most of the participants were females, numbers of the participants varied under each group because they were randomly sampled from each of the three Federal Colleges of Education selected, the contributing effect of gender on students' academic achievement in Algebraic expressions was found to be 0.3%; It was concluded that gender as a factor independently and significantly does not affect the students' academic achievement in Algebraic expressions in Federal Colleges of Education, Southwest Nigeria. It was recommended among others that Federal Colleges of Education Southwest, Nigeria should continue to adopt gender-neutral teaching approaches, ensuring that both male and female students are equally supported in the teaching and learning of Algebraic expressions.

Keywords: Gender, Algebraic expressions and students' academic achievement

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Introduction

Gender serves as an analytical framework that delineates the sociological roles, cultural responsibilities, and expectations assigned to men and women within a specific society or cultural context. Gender encompasses the personality traits, attributes, behaviours, values, relative power, influence, roles, and expectations (femininity and masculinity) that society assigns to the two sexes in a differential manner. Consequently, gender serves as a psychological construct and a cultural constant shaped by societal influences to distinguish the roles, behaviours, and mental and emotional characteristics of males and females. Breda, Jouini, & Napp, 2023.

The common misunderstanding surrounding Mathematics is the belief that it solely revolves around formulas and computations that must be committed to memory. This perspective has undermined and obstructed the endeavours of students more than any other factor Wrigley-Asante, Ackah, & Frimpong, 2023 and Breda, Jouini, & Napp, 2023. This misconception has progressed to categorize Mathematics as a subject predominantly for males within the educational context of Nigerian society Gevrek, Gevrek, & Neumeier, 2020. Significant progress has been made in our country regarding the integration of gender considerations in education in recent years. At this moment in time, opportunities abound for women to pursue and achieve careers that were once deemed unattainable by previous generations Oribhabor, 2019. The topic of gender influences various contexts Chidumebi, Ijeoma, 2020.

Moreover, as gender disparities in science, technology and Mathematics related fields continue to garner attention, understanding the potential influence of gender differences in the context of algebraic expression learning becomes crucial Hall, & Norén, 2021. A significant number of studies have concentrated on the disparities between genders in the achievement of Algebraic expressions. The achievement in algebraic expressions among college students showed no significant difference between female and male students; however, there was a decline observed in the 200 Level cohort. Research indicated that students' proficiency in Algebraic expressions matched that of their male counterparts in the first year; however, this achievement declined in the second year Kyaruzi, 2023. The findings from TIMSS indicated that there will be no disparity in the average mathematical achievement between male and female students at the NCE 300 Level across the countries examined (Asante, Ackah & Frimpong, 2023).

Studies conducted in Africa revealed a significant gender difference in Algebraic expression achievement, favouring male students compared to their female counterparts. Research findings indicated that the academic achievement of female students in Algebraic

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DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15693161>

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expressions was notably inferior compared to that of male students. The disparity in achievement between females and males can be attributed to differences in mathematical attitudes. While significant attention has been directed towards the accomplishments of females in Algebraic expression, studies have also highlighted the underachievement of males in comparison to their female counterparts (Asante, Ackah & Frimpong, 2023). Furthermore, the possible impact of gender differences on the effectiveness of these strategies in College-level Algebra education should not be ignored, given that gender disparities in Mathematics achievement have been a topic of continuous investigation (Gevrek, Gevrek, & Neumeier, 2020).

Aim and Objective of the Study

The study aimed to investigate the effect of gender on students' academic achievement in Algebraic expressions in Federal Colleges of Education Southwest, Nigeria. The objective of the study was to examine the main effect of gender on students' academic achievement in Algebraic expressions in Federal Colleges of Education Southwest, Nigeria.

Hypothesis

Based on the above stated objective, the following null hypothesis at 0.05 level of significance was tested

Ho₁: There will be no significant main effect of gender on students' academic achievement in Algebraic expressions.

Methodology

This study delves into the methodology employed in this investigation. It encompasses the design of the study, the population involved, the sampling method, and a detailed description of the research instrument. Validity of research Instrument, reliability of research Instrument, administration of research Instrument collection and analyzing data.

Research Design

This study used a mixed-method research methodology, specifically a 3x3x1 factorial quasi-experimental design, incorporating pre-test and post-test measures, with a non-randomized control group and non-equivalent intact groups. The dependent variable was the students' academic achievement in pre-test and post-test approach.

Population of the Study

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The study's population consisted of all first-year students enrolled in Federal Colleges of Education located in Southwest Nigeria, specifically including Federal College of Education (Special) Oyo in Oyo State, Federal College of Education Osiele in Abeokuta, Ogun State, and Federal College of Education Iwo in Osun State. The population of first-year students at Federal College of Education Special, Oyo, was five hundred and fifty (550) students. In contrast, the total student population at Federal College of Education Abeokuta was four hundred and fifty (450), while Federal College of Education Iwo, Osun State, had a total of three hundred and fifty (350) students. The overall target population for this study consists of one thousand three hundred and fifty (1350) students from the schools under consideration at the time of conducting this research.

Sample and Sampling Techniques

A multi-stage sampling technique was employed to choose the participants for the study. The initial phase included employing a simple random sampling technique to select three Federal Colleges of Education that fulfilled the criteria of having qualified lecturers proficient in diverse methods of teaching and learning Algebraic expressions. Secondly, a random sampling procedure was employed to select the Basic General Mathematics students for participation in the study. Finally, the study consists of three intact classes of 100 level Basic General Mathematics students. The two Federal Colleges of Education that were used for the experimental groups have been established over four decades while the one used for control group was established less than ten years ago.

Research Instruments

This study utilized two research instruments: the Basic General Mathematics Students' Academic Achievement Test (BGMSAAT), and a Lesson Plan Format (LPF). These tools were designed to facilitate the teaching and learning of Algebraic expressions, which is central to the study.

Basic General Mathematics Students' Academic Achievement Test (BGMAAT)

Assessment for Academic Achievement in Basic General Mathematics. The achievement tests were created to evaluate students' understanding of concepts related to Algebraic expressions. The focus was on the primary subject of Basic General Mathematics II, specifically 'Algebraic Expressions,' which is part of the curriculum for NCE 1 in the second semester. The assessment comprises 50 multiple-choice questions, each offering four options labelled A to D. These questions are designed to align with six levels of cognitive domains: Knowledge, Comprehension, Application, Analysis, Synthesis, and Evaluation.

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Lesson Plan Format (LPF)

A lesson plan was developed by the researcher in order to guide the teaching of Algebraic expressions in NCE 1 with course code GSE 122.

Description of the Research Instruments

Basic General Mathematics Students' Academic Achievement Test (BGMSAAT) were answered by the students in Basic General Mathematics II. It was divided into four (3) sections. Section A consists of demographic data which include gender, level, and name of institution. Section B comprises of 50 multiple choice questions which was self-structured to test the students' academic achievement in Algebraic expressions, and Section C contained the Lesson Plan Format (LPF)

Method of Data Analysis

The collected data underwent analysis through descriptive statistics, employing frequency counts, tallies, and percentages. The hypotheses developed for the study underwent testing through Analysis of Covariance (ANCOVA) at a significance level of 0.05.

Presentation of Results

The below are the socio-demographic characteristics of the participants.

Table 1:

Distribution of the Participants by Gender

Gender	Frequency	Percent	Cumulative Percent
Female	244	64.2	64.2
Male	136	35.8	100.0
Total	380	100.0	

Source: Field Survey, 2024

Table 1 reveals that 244 (64.2%) of the participants were females, while 136 (35.8%) were males. This means that most of the participants were females because females have interest in teaching profession than male students.

H₀₁: There will be no significant main effect of gender on students' academic achievement in Algebraic expressions

Table 2a:

Analysis of covariance of main effect of gender on students' academic achievement in Algebraic expressions

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Source	Type III Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	Partial Eta Squared
Corrected Model	16.141 ^a	2	8.071	.573	.565	.003
Intercept	5211.924	1	5211.924	369.769	.000	.495
Pre-test	15.995	1	15.995	1.135	.287	.003
Gender	.033	1	.033	.002	.961	.000
Error	5313.845	377	14.095			
Total	211209.000	380				
Corrected Total	5329.987	379				

a. R Squared = .003 (Adjusted R Squared = -.002)

Source: Field Survey, 2024

Table 2a shows that there will be no significant main effect of gender on students’ academic achievement in Algebraic expressions ($F_{(1, 379)} = 0.002$ $p < 0.05$, $\eta^2 = 0.200$). The null hypothesis was therefore accepted. This implies that gender as a factor independently and significantly does not affect the students’ academic achievement in Algebraic expressions in Federal Colleges of Education, Southwest Nigeria. Also, the eta squared value of 0.003 shows the contributing effect size of only 0.3%.

Table 2b:

Estimated Marginal Means of gender on students’ academic achievement in Algebraic expressions

Group	Mean	Std. Error	95% Confidence Interval	
			Lower Bound	Upper Bound
Female	23.283 ^a	.240	22.811	23.756
Male	23.264 ^a	.322	22.630	23.897

Source: Field Survey, 2024

Table 2b shows that although female participants had higher post-test mean (\bar{x}) score of 23.283 than the male counterparts with post-test mean (\bar{x}) score of 23.264, there is little or no difference among the two gender. The difference is not statistically significant nor practically significant. This means that after neglecting other factors, gender is not a key factor that significantly affects the students’ academic achievement in Algebraic expressions among students of Federal Colleges of Education in South-West Nigeria.

Discussion of Findings

The study aimed to investigate the effect of gender on students’ academic achievement in Algebraic expressions in Federal Colleges of Education Southwest Nigeria. This section presented the discussion of the results relating it with previous studies. The demographic information of the students revealed in the table 1 of the study that more female, two

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hundred and forty-four (244) (64.2%) participated while one hundred and thirty-six students (136) (35.8%) were males.

The number of male and female students participated were not equal because of the variation in the population of the students in each of the Federal Colleges of Education selected. The implication of this result was that Federal Colleges of Education Southwest, Nigeria produces more female teachers than male teachers because females have interest in teaching profession than male students. Female teachers see teaching profession as more convenient as it helps them to manage family while earning a living such that they would be able to take care of their family in the nearest future (Ezekiel, 2021).

The numbers of the participants varied under each group because they were randomly sampled from each Federal College of Education population. Which implies that the population of the participants were higher in Federal College of Education Special, Oyo than that of Federal College of Education, Abeokuta and Federal College of Education, Iwo. The two experimental groups were Federal Colleges of Education Oyo Special and Abeokuta while Federal College of Education Iwo served as control group. This position was in agreement with many previous studies that have to do with experimental studies (Osuafor & Orji, 2017, Rodríguez, Piñeiro, Estévez & Valle, 2020).and Kunwar 2022).

The Null Hypothesis which stated that there will be no significant main effect of gender on students' academic achievement in Algebraic expressions. The result in table 2a and b ($F_{(1, 379)} = 0.002$ $p < 0.05$, $\eta^2 = 0.200$) revealed that there was significant main effect of gender on students' academic achievement in Algebraic expressions. The null hypothesis was therefore accepted. This implies that gender as a factor independently and significantly does not affect the students' academic achievement in Algebraic expressions in Federal Colleges of Education, Southwest Nigeria. Also, the eta squared value of 0.003 shows the contributing effect size of only 0.3%. expressions while the estimated marginal means shows that gender as a factor was seen not to be independently and significantly affect the students' academic achievement in algebraic expression.

Although, female participants had higher post-test mean than the male counterparts a little or no difference is evident among the two genders were recorded. The difference is not statistically nor practically significant. Implying that aside other factors, gender is not a key factor that significantly affects the students' academic achievement in Algebraic expressions among Federal Colleges of Education in Southwest, Nigeria. This aligns with a study that compared the contents tested in TIMSS, including geometry, measurement, fractions, and algebra. The findings indicate that Singaporean students consistently scored significantly higher than Malaysian students, irrespective of gender.

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Numerous studies have indicated varying levels of achievement in science subjects among secondary school students based on gender, whereas other research has found no significant gender impact on achievement at this educational stage (Wen, & Dubé, 2022). This may be one of the reasons in more recent editions of the Research in Mathematics Education in Australasia (RiMEA) 4-year reviews that the National Council of Teachers of Mathematics (NCTM) handbooks have not prioritized gender, instead incorporating it into a wider discussion on equity. However, studies conducted in Africa revealed a significant gender difference in Algebraic expression achievement, favoring males compared to female students (Wrigley-Asante, Ackah, & Frimpong, 2023) Research findings indicated that the academic achievement of female students in Algebraic expressions was notably inferior to that of male students. The disparity in achievement between females and males can be attributed to differences in mathematical attitudes. While significant attention has been directed towards the accomplishments of females in Algebraic expression, it has also been noted that males exhibit underachievement in comparison to their female counterparts (Wen, & Dubé, 2022).

Conclusion

The results indicated that there was no significant main effect of gender on students' academic achievement in Algebraic expressions ($F(1, 379) = 0.002, p < 0.05, \eta^2 = 0.200$). The null hypothesis was consequently accepted. This indicated that gender, as an independent variable, does not significantly affected students' academic achievement in Algebraic expressions at Federal Colleges of Education Southwest, Nigeria. The eta squared value of 0.003 indicates a contributing impact size of just 0.3%.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of the study, the following recommendations was made Lecturers in Federal Colleges of Education should continue to adopt gender-neutral teaching approaches, ensuring that both male and female students are equally supported in their learning.

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